

PREFACE:

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The *Encyclopedia Americana* is intended to serve as a general reference resource for schools, colleges, and public libraries. In an era of increasingly specialized reference works, and of even more highly specialized journals and academic publications, it is occasionally forgotten that often the best introduction to a subject is the well-conceived, well-written overview provided by the general encyclopedia. Such an encyclopedia also has the ability to provide needed context, owing to the scope and depth of its coverage. The publication of the 2003 edition of the *Encyclopedia Americana* marks the set's 174th year in print and its 68th consecutive annual revision. While such figures do not absolutely ensure the integrity of an encyclopedia, the longevity of the *Americana* is surely a good indicator of the respect it has earned in the libraries of Canada and the United States. The present edition continues traditions of service and accountability to the educational community established nearly two centuries ago.

The tens of thousands of articles in the *Americana* serve as a bridge between the worlds of the specialist and the general reader. Distinguished advisers have assisted the editors in organizing the information in their fields into convenient forms of presentation. In some instances articles of almost book length have resulted from the conferences between advisers and editors—for example, the articles on the United States and on the two world wars. In other instances the decision was to present facts briefly and specifically—for example, a definition of a technical term or the identification of a character in fiction. Thousands of such short entries are provided to meet the reader's needs for specific information.

The advisers have also assisted the editors in choosing leading authorities in each field to write the articles. After the contributor is selected—whether the area is physics or the theater, European history or sports—he or she is reminded of the need to write for the nonspecialist reader. The author is asked not to “write down” but to present facts and interpretations in an orderly way and in a direct style, as well as to explain technical terms when they are used. All articles in the *Americana* are carefully checked by the editors with these considerations in mind.

Because of this policy the *Americana's* articles communicate to a wide range of readers. Young students are able to find the information they are seeking, and to understand what they read. Teachers, librarians, and adults in general satisfy their reference needs without losing time trying to comprehend technicalities for which they have no specialized preparation.

For this edition, in accordance with the *Americana's* policy of continuous revision, many new articles have been prepared by either contributing authors or the editors, including those on subjects not covered in previous editions under their own headings. In addition, hundreds of articles have been revised by their original authors or by the editors. In a few instances articles formerly prepared by contributors have been amended by the editors, and in each such instance an asterisk (*) follows the name of the author.

In covering all areas the editors have sought to present information in an objective manner. As the *Americana's* first editor, Francis Lieber (1798–1872), said in 1829, "My wish has been not to obtrude opinions but to furnish facts." At the same time, those facts need to be set in meaningful perspective, and this is what the contributors and editors have sought to do.

This edition of the *Encyclopedia Americana* is published in the belief that it provides an accurate and comprehensive picture of past and present times. Its editorial staff, advisory editors, and more than six thousand contributors have cooperated in producing an encyclopedia that is reliable, readable, and relevant to today's needs.

ARRANGEMENT OF CONTENTS

Volume 1, after this preface, contains the list of the *Americana* editorial staff members (page vii), the list of advisory editors (pages viii–ix), and the list of contributors (beginning on page x). These are followed by a key to pronunciation and a list of abbreviations used in the encyclopedia. Volume 30 contains the index. Preceding the index in that volume is a guide to the use of the index and a special list of abbreviations used in the index.

In the main text of the encyclopedia, articles are arranged alphabetically *word by word* rather than letter by letter: *North Dakota* precedes *Northcliffe*, *Wood Engraving* precedes *Woodbury*, and so on. In a series of articles with the same heading, the order of *persons*, *places*, and *things* is followed: *Bell, Alexander Graham* precedes *Bell (city)*, which precedes *Bell (thing)*. Further details on the alphabetizing system are given in the Guide to the Use of the Index (volume 30).

Names of persons and places are generally spelled in the encyclopedia as they are spelled in the country of origin. But standard anglicized forms are used for names of rulers, countries, and some major cities and geographical features—for example, *Henry*, not *Henri*, for kings of France; *Florence*, not *Firenze*, for the city in Italy. Names and other terms from languages that do not employ the Roman alphabet are transcribed according to established systems of transliteration.

The year-to-year revisions of the *Americana* sometimes require adding pages and, in some instances, dropping pages. As a result parts of the volumes have to be renumbered. Thus, when a new article fills more pages than the article or articles it has replaced, the new pages may be numbered with a figure plus a letter—for example, 237*a*, 237*b*, and so on. Sometimes old material is dropped and new material added, or an article is transferred to a new heading, as when required by a change in a country's name. When the new or remaining material occupies fewer pages than the old, a page may be given a "telescoped" number such as 380–390.

RESEARCH AIDS

The *Index* (volume 30) should always be consulted first in looking for information in the *Americana*. This index, with more than 350,000 entries, provides a complete guide to the contents of the encyclopedia. For every article in the set,

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there is an index entry, which also lists the other places in the encyclopedia where information on the subject can be found. In addition, the index has tens of thousands of entries on subjects that are covered in the encyclopedia but do not have separate articles of their own. Many subjects, especially major ones, are organized in the index in the form of extensive outlines.

Cross-References in the text of the encyclopedia—within articles, at the end of articles, or as separate entries—also lead the reader to related articles or provide the heading under which a subject is treated. Cross-references generally give the full title of the articles referred to, printed in capitals—for example, “See also UNITED STATES.” Sometimes the abbreviations *q.v.* or *qq.v.* (for the Latin words meaning “which see”) are used.

Tables of Contents at the beginning of long articles help readers find coverage of specific topics they are investigating. Most of these tables contain page references to specific sections of the articles.

Bibliographies at the end of articles refer the reader to books or other materials for further research. Wherever possible books suitable for the general reader are included along with more advanced or specialized works. In addition every effort is made to ensure that divergent points of view on the subject discussed are represented in the bibliography.

SPECIAL FEATURES

The *Encyclopedia Americana* provides several features that organize information in a special way to benefit its readers. For example, separate articles appear on each of the centuries of the common era under their own headings, such as FIRST CENTURY and TWENTIETH CENTURY. These surveys cut across national boundaries to set political, social, and cultural events within an international perspective.

Separate articles on classic works of literature, philosophy, and economics and on major operas discuss these works more fully than can be done in the author's or composer's biography. There also are separate articles on the books of the Bible (for which references usually are based on the Revised Standard Version) and on significant historical documents, such as the Declaration of Independence and the Constitution of the United States, with some including the complete text of the document. Each letter of the alphabet is discussed in a separate article devoted to the letter's orthographic and linguistic history.

Articles on specialized areas of education, such as those on BUSINESS EDUCATION, LEGAL EDUCATION, MEDICAL EDUCATION, and THEOLOGICAL EDUCATION, offer useful discussions of these fields for those contemplating advanced study in them or for those researching the various educational issues associated with each. These articles serve to complement the nearly booklength EDUCATION article itself as well as the various related education articles, such as PRESCHOOL EDUCATION.

In entries for each of the states of the United States, there are sidebars identifying both prominent people associated with the state and key events in the state's history. Likewise shown are the names of all of those who have served as governor of the state, from the colonial era to the present.

ILLUSTRATIONS AND MAPS

Illustrations, in color or black-and-white, are used functionally in the encyclopedia to clarify and supplement the text. Drawings, diagrams, graphs, maps, and charts convey information that words cannot express as well. Photographs reveal the atmosphere of places and the personalities of people, show what objects look like, and make the reader a witness to important events in history.

Color maps appear with articles on continents, major countries, all U.S. states and Canadian provinces, and some major cities; black-and-white maps accompany many articles on smaller countries, islands, and other major cities. Most color maps are prepared by Hammond World Atlas Corporation. A convenient feature of many maps is an inset map that shows the location of the mapped area in relation to a larger unit—country, continent, hemisphere, or world. Most color maps are accompanied by map indexes listing the major geographical features shown and the inhabited places and their populations, with coordinates for locating them on the map. The map coordinates lead to the place-name, not to the dot or other locator symbol.

POPULATION FIGURES

Every effort is made to provide the latest available census figures or the most recent reliable estimates. For example, population data for the United States, the individual states, and cities and towns are based on the 2000 census. Populations for places in Canada are derived from that country's 2001 census.

PRONUNCIATIONS

Entries for names and terms whose pronunciation may be in doubt among users of the encyclopedia are supplied with pronunciations following the headword or, in the case of some surnames, as part of the headword. For foreign names the *Americana* generally gives the pronunciation used by native speakers of the language in question rather than the anglicized version. In some cases, however, both are shown. The symbols used and the sounds they represent are shown on page xcvi.

THE EDITORS

EVALUATION OF ENCYCLOPEDIA AMERICANA:

- AUTHORITY

Title: ENCYCLOPEDIA AMERICANA

Genre/ Form: Encyclopedias and dictionaries

Subject: General

Language: English

Volume: 30

Edition: 2003 (First Edition: 1829, Latest Print Edition: 2006)

Place of Publication: Danbury, Connecticut (United States)

Copyright: GROLIER INCORPORATED

Publisher: Scholastic Library Publishing

Author: Grolier Incorporated.

Editor-in-Chief: Michael Shally-Jensen

- **BRIEF INTRODUCTION**

- One of the largest general encyclopedias in the English language, ENCYCLOPEDIA AMERICANA was first compiled and edited by Francis Lieber.
- It was the first major multivolume encyclopedia to be published in UNITED STATES (1829-1833) comprising of 13 volumes.
- Lieber's work was based on the seventh edition of the well established *KONVERSATIONS-LEXIKON* (German language encyclopedia published by the F.A. Brockhaus printing house) of Brockhaus.
- Subsequent editions were published and the encyclopedia got expanded in 1902 (16 volumes), 1911(20 volumes), 1918-1920(30 volumes) and thereafter was continuously revised.
- An Annual or Yearbook, which appeared under variety of titles was also published each year beginning in 1923 and continuing until 2008.
- In 1995, it's publisher, Grolier.Inc. made *AMERICANA* available in CD-ROM.
- The online version of encyclopedia ENCYCLOPEDIA AMERICANA ONLINE became available in 1996.
- After SCHOLASTIC CORPORATION acquired GROLIER in 2000 for US \$400 million, the online version of AMERICANA became part of a suite of educational resources.
- The final print edition was released in 2006.
- In 2008, Encyclopedia Americana went exclusively online in order to cut costs on maintaining a physical reference book.
- Today ENCYCLOPEDIA AMERICANA lives on as an integral database within the Grolier Online product.

- **SCOPE:**

- The encyclopedia Americana is known for its authoritativeness and readability which is relevant to today's needs.
- *Americana's* content is international in scope.
- *Encyclopedia Americana* is general in nature covering almost all areas of knowledge world.
- The information in encyclopedia is presented in most convenient form aiming non specialist reader.
- The encyclopedia has more than 45,000 articles and major of these articles are signed, many by scholars preeminent in their fields.
- Articles in the encyclopedia runs into considerable length to meet the reader's information need, ranging from 500 words to 300,000 words depending upon scope of the topic.
- Written by about 6,000 contributors, the Encyclopedia Americana includes over 9.000 Bibliographies, 150,000 cross-references, 1,000+tables, 1,200 maps and almost 4,500 black and white line art and color images. It also has 680 fact boxes.

- **Treatment:**

- The names and places are generally spelled in the encyclopedia as they are spelled in the country of origin but standard anglicized (To make English in appearance) forms are used for names of rules, counties and for geographical features. For example *Henry* not *Henri*, for kings of France.
- After revision in new edition, if the new article fills more pages than the article it replaced, the new pages are numbered with a figure plus letter- for example, 237a, 237b and so on.
- On the other side if the new or remaining article after easing obsolete or non-usable information, occupies fewer pages than the old, the page may be given a “telescoped” number like 380-386.
- For every article in the set there is an index entry (Volume 30), which also lists the other places in the encyclopedia where information on the subject can be found. It is always advised to first consult Index in looking for information in the *Americana*.
- Cross references – within articles, at the end of articles or as separate entries lead the reader to related article or provide the heading under which a subject is treated. Cross references generally give the full title of the articles referred to, printed in capitals but sometimes abbreviations can also be used.
- Table of Contents at the beginning of long articles helps the readers find coverage of specific topics they are investigating.
- Entries for names and terms whose pronunciation may be in doubt among users of the encyclopedia are supplied with pronunciations following the headword.
- Bibliographies at the end of articles refer the reader to the books or articles or other materials for further research. Every effort is made to ensure that divergent points of view on the subject are represented in the bibliography.
- In successive editions, hundreds of articles have been revised by their original authors or are amended by the editors. In each such instances an asterisk (*) follows the name of author.
- Population data for the United States, Individual states, cities and towns based on 2000 census and of Canada from country’s 2001 census are provided.

- **Arrangement:**

- *Encyclopedia Americana* is arranged in set of 30 volumes.
- Volume 1 contains the preface which is followed by the list of Americana editorial staff members (page vii), the list of advisory editors (page viii-ix) and list of contributors (beginning on page x), followed by key to pronunciation and a list of abbreviations used in the encyclopedia.
- In the main text of the encyclopedia, articles are arranged alphabetically word by word rather than letter by letter: *North Dakota* precedes *Northcliffe*.
- In a series of articles with the same heading, the order of persons, places and the things is followed: *Bell, Alexander Graham* (person) precedes *Bell* (city), which precedes *Bell* (thing). Further details of alphabetizing system are given in the Guide to the Use of the Index (Volume 30).
- Volume 30 contains the Index. Preceding the index is a guide to use the index and a special list of abbreviations used in the index.

- **Format:** It is available in both print and digital form (online + CD-ROM).

- **PRINT FORMAT:**

- The reference book is handy and easy to consult.
- Burgundy and Black Binding with Gold Embossment is hardcover with paperback.
- Good quality of paper is used.
- The information is given in two columns on single page
- Use of drawings, graphs, maps, tables, and illustrations in color of black and white are used in encyclopedia to clarify and supplement the text.

- **ONLINE FORMAT:**

- The online version of the Encyclopedia Americana, first introduced in 1996, continues to be up to date. The online format is available at Scholastic.com requiring a subscription.
- It is available to libraries as one of the options in the Grolier Online reference Service. Grolier Online service is not available to individual subscribers.
- Encyclopedia Americana (online) provides thousands of authoritative, in depth articles geared to more sophisticated high school, college and adult uses.
- Encyclopedia Americana is updated Quarterly to ensure that subscribers have access to current and authoritative information on subjects from A to Z.
- With online format, users have easy access to information with the factual integrity they need to research topics for school work, special projects or to satisfy their own curiosity.
- The Encyclopedia Americana online is a visually-friendly website aimed toward educators and students. Users can find over 500,000 links to reference materials, Web sites and periodicals for the student environment and lesson plans, project ideas and activities for educators.
- A redesigned interface and partly reengineered product, featuring enhanced search capabilities and a first-ever ADA-compliant, text-only version for users with disabilities, was presented in 2002.

- **CD-ROM FORMAT:**

- A CD-ROM version of the encyclopedia was published in 1995.
- The text and images were stored on separate disks.

- **Special features:**

- Information is organized in a special way to benefit the readers. For example, separate articles appear on each of the centuries of the Common Era under their own headings such as FIRST CENTURY and TWENTIETH CENTURY. These surveys cut across national boundaries to set political, social and cultural events within an international perspective.
- Glossary defining technical or difficult terms accompany some articles like for sports or for business subjects. A full list of glossaries appears in the index entry *Glossary*.
- For many maps in the Encyclopedia, there is an inset map that shows the location of the mapped area in relation to a larger unit – country, continent, hemisphere, or world.
- Color maps are accompanied by map indexes listing the major geographical features.
- In entries for each of the states of the United States, there are sidebars identifying both prominent people associated with the state and key events in the state's history. Likewise shown are the names of all of those who have served as governor of the state from the colonial era to the present.

- **Drawbacks:**

- With the ever growing information need of readers and thirst for current and updated information, the printed version of encyclopedia is no longer sustainable which is published after one year gap.
- As it is General in nature, there is not detailed treatment to each and every subject. Often minor subjects get poor treatment.
- *Encyclopedia Americana* is biased toward toward North America that is intensive information is provided about U.S.A and Canada as compared to other countries.
- The publication of printed edition was stopped after 2006 which was a major setback to the libraries located in remote areas unable to afford ICT infrastructure.
- Pages are crowded with dense text relieved by little white space; page number placement jumps annoyingly from header to footer when illustrations bleed to page edges.
- Most of the photographs are black and white, and many are quite dark or have high contrast. This more than anything else gives a dated and drab look to the pages, even when the photos are of recent vintage.

- **Conclusion:**

- The Encyclopedia Americana is one of the most thorough reference set ever which is trusted by readers for study and research. It is known for its excellent in-depth scholarly coverage with balanced global perspective and unique insight. This document is published in belief that it will provide an accurate and comprehensive picture of past and present times. With its general nature including information about every discipline in knowledge world and suitable for every age group with diverse background. Encyclopedia Americana is remains a good choice to be included in collection of Public libraries and Academic Libraries.

- **References:**

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